

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART XII

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Some quinoline-arsenic acid derivatives have been synthesised, which are expected to possess anti-malarial properties.

It is sometimes considered desirable to reinforce the specific action of quinine by means of arsenic. The chief value of such a combination is in the treatment of chronic malaria cases, where there is infection of the liver or spleen with accompanying anaemia and cachexia. Dr. A. N. Bose of this laboratory (*private communication*) observed that monkeys infected with the highly virulent strain of *P. Knowlesi* and having repeated relapses even after treatment with 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5 (δ -diethylaminobutyl) amino-acridine (*cf.* Siddons and Bose, *Indian Med. Gaz.*, 1944, 79, 101) would be permanently cured of the infection by additional injection of an arsenical drug. It was therefore suggested to try for antimalarial activity of quinoline and acridine compounds containing arsenic attached to the nuclei. In view of the observation that the seat of antimalarial action of quinine is in the quinoline nucleus, it has been considered desirable to synthesise some quinoline derivatives having arsenic attached to the quinoline nucleus and to see if they exhibit antimalarial activity (*cf.* Slater, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1209; Barnett, Gillieson and Kermack, *ibid.*, 1934, 433).

Few quinoline-arsenic acid derivatives are known in literature and they have been prepared by Bart's reaction, which is rather tedious and generally gives very poor yield of the products. Moreover, the necessary amines required for this synthesis by Bart's reaction may not be readily available in stable forms. It has been shown in Part XI (Ghosh and Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 257) that the method of Döbner and Miller (*Ber.*, 1881, 14, 2812) can be successfully applied for the synthesis of quinoline-arsenic acid derivatives. In continuation of this work, 2-phenylquinoline-6-arsenic acid (I) and 2-phenyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-arsenic acid (II) have now been synthesised by reacting cinnamic aldehyde with *p*-arsanilic acid and 3-amino-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid respectively, according to the method of Döbner and Miller.

(I)

(II)

It is surmised by pharmacologists that quinquevalent arsonic acids become therapeutically active only on reduction, in the body, to the trivalent state. It might seem natural therefore to reduce the acids first and then to administer the reduced products, provided the latter do not prove toxic to the host. Unfortunately, the difficulty has been to obtain easily soluble and stable derivatives of these trivalent compounds. In view of these

observations, the compound (I) has been reduced with hypophosphorus acid to yield the dihydrochloride of 2 : 2'-diphenyl-6 : 6'-arsenoquinoline (III) which, though found fairly stable on storage, is practically insoluble in water.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Phenylquinoline-6-arsonic Acid (I).—Commercial concentrated hydrochloric acid (28 c.c.) was poured dropwise into a flask containing well-powdered *p*-arsanilic acid (30 g.), when the hydrochloride of *p*-arsanilic acid was obtained. To this mixture was added dropwise cinnamic aldehyde (20 g.) with stirring, when there was a slight rise in temperature and the mass changed to orange-red. The mixture was then heated on the oil-bath at 105-10° for 3 hours, when a thick, clear solution was obtained. It was next heated at 120-25° for 3 hours and then allowed to stand overnight.

Next day the solution was diluted with a large quantity of water, when some amount of tarry mass was precipitated. The mixture was allowed to stand for sometime and then the supernatant clear solution was decanted. The solution was then carefully neutralised, under cooling, with a cold 20% aqueous caustic soda solution, when a flocculent precipitate was obtained, which on standing became granular. The solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and was finally crystallised from a large quantity of alcohol in colourless, crystalline powder (yield 6 g.), which does not melt even at 340° but changes to light brown at about 300°. (Found : N, 4.27 ; As, 22.97. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4NA_2$ requires, N, 4.25 ; As, 22.79 per cent). It is practically insoluble in boiling water. It does not contain any diazotisable amino group. A dilute hydrochloric acid solution of this compound gives a brown precipitate with Mayer's reagent.

The yield of the above compound was raised to 10 g., when the reaction was carried out at 115-20° for 6 hours.

2-Phenyl-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-arsonic Acid (II).—In this reaction 3-amino-4-hydroxyphenylarsonic acid (25 g.), commercial concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) and cinnamic aldehyde (20 g.) were used and the mixture was heated at 115-20° for 6 hours. Subsequent procedure was the same as described above. After neutralisation with 10% aqueous caustic soda solution, no precipitate was, however, obtained. The clear solution was then saturated with pure sodium chloride and allowed to stand overnight. Next day a precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and finally crystallised from boiling water in brownish crystalline powder (yield 5 g.). It was dried *in vacuo* at 120° and then analysed. (Found : As, 21.29. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4NA_2$ requires As, 21.73 per cent). It does not melt even at 330° and does not contain any diazotisable amino group. Its aqueous solution gives a deep red colouration with ferric chloride.

2 : 2'-Diphenyl-6 : 6'-arsenoquinoline Dihydrochloride (III).—The compound (I, 5 g.),

in 50 c.c. of water and 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, was reduced with 35% hypophosphorus acid (33 g.) and 3 c.c. of 1% aqueous solution of potassium iodide, by warming the solution on the water-bath and passing in a stream of carbon dioxide. Within 15 minutes the reduced product separated out as a yellow solid, which was cooled, filtered and washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, water and finally with alcohol; yield 3 g. It is a fine, yellow powder, practically insoluble in boiling water, alcohol or concentrated hydrochloric acid. It is soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid. On heating, it turns brown at 150°, becomes viscous at 220-22° and decomposes at 250°. It was dried at 100° *in vacuo* and then analysed. (Found: N, 4.41; As, 24.27. $C_{30}H_{20}N_2As_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires, N, 4.44; As, 23.8 per cent).

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